

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: SHIN****FIRST NAME: WOOSEOK****PROGRAM CODE: DILT****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did use Zotero to insert references

The author did use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 2%

The author used the following software: MSWord 2016 on Windows 11

QUIZ FOR COURSE ACA-401D

1. What initial step must be taken before any other steps in writing a good academic essay, and why is it important?
 - Drafting the introduction sets the tone for the essay.
 - Conducting thorough research on the relevant topic to expand understanding and gather sound evidence to support the argument.¹**
 - Writing the conclusion ensures the essay has a clear endpoint, summarizing the main points, and providing a final perspective on the topic.
 - Proofreading the essay to eliminate any grammatical errors, enhancing readability, and professionalism.

¹ Laurent Cleenewerch and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*, 5th ed. (Washington D.C.: Euclid University Press, 2024), 6.

2. When constructing an argument, what is the primary purpose of including a warrant, and how does it differ from evidence?
- Additional evidence for the claim should be provided to make the argument more coherent and convincing.
 - To clearly state the position on the issue.
 - To ensure the reason is relevant to the claim, thereby preventing the reader from rejecting the argument due to perceived irrelevance.²**
 - To summarize the entire argument in a concise manner.
3. What essential elements should be included in the Introduction of an academic paper to guide the readers through the paper effectively?
- A detailed literature review is provided to provide context and clarify the problem.
 - A statement of the research question or its condition, the significance of the proposed research question, and a claim or assertion.³**
 - A summary of the findings gives an overview of the research.
 - Detailed methodologies are provided to provide general ideas for the sake of the readers' logical flow of thinking.
4. What is the significance of the findings section in a dissertation, and how should the data be presented to the reader?

² Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*, 9th ed. (Chicago: The University of Chicago Press, 2018), 64.

³ Ibid., 111-113.

- To provide a summary of the literature review for context.
 - To link specific findings to the corresponding research questions and hypotheses.⁴**
 - To outline the research methodology used in the study.
 - To discuss the implications of the research findings.
5. What is the purpose of the implications section in a dissertation, and what areas can it potentially impact?
- To summarize the research findings in a concise manner.
 - To suggest insights gained from the research that can advance theory, research, practice, and public policy.⁵**
 - To list the references used throughout the dissertation.
 - To describe the research methodology in detail.
6. Which of the following statements most accurately describes the concept of plagiarism and the recommended practices to avoid it in academic writing?
- Plagiarism is defined as the act of using a source of information without proper credit to the original author.⁶**
 - Plagiarism occurs when an author uses too many direct quotations in their academic essay, thereby failing to demonstrate original thought.

⁴ James Sampson, *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research*, 2nd ed. (Tallahassee: Florida State University, 2017), 54.

⁵ *Ibid.*, 60.

⁶ Cleenewerch and Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack*, 36-38.

- Plagiarism is the process of paraphrasing information from a source without altering the original meaning.
 - Plagiarism involves citing information that is considered common knowledge.
7. What is the role of delimitations in a dissertation, and how do they contribute to the research process?
- To define the boundaries to clarify the scope and limitations of the study.**⁷
 - To summarize the findings in a concise manner.
 - To provide a detailed literature review for context.
 - To outline the research methodology used in the study.
8. What should be the focus of the literature review in a dissertation, and how does it support the research questions?
- Thoroughly examine past studies and emphasize significant theories and research that have contributed to current knowledge while also identifying gaps and issues with previous methods.**⁸
 - Summarizing the research findings to provide an overview.
 - Describing the research methodology in detail.
 - Listing all references used to ensure proper citation.

⁷ Sampson, *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research*, 49.

⁸ Ibid., 31.

9. What is one of the most significant recommendations for enhancing efficiency and maintaining sharpness in analysis while writing an academic essay?

- Writing the introduction first sets the tone.
- Taking notes or comments while reading enhances efficiency and maintains sharpness in analysis.⁹**
- Drafting the conclusion early ensures a clear endpoint.
- Proofread the essay multiple times.

10. In the context of constructing an argument, what is the distinction between a reason and evidence according to Turabian?

- A reason is a statement that leads readers to accept a claim, while evidence is the data on which the reason is based.¹⁰**
- A reason is the data supporting the claim, while evidence is the statement leading to the claim.
- Both reason and evidence are interchangeable terms.
- Evidence is a statement that leads readers to accept a claim, while a reason is the data on which the evidence is based.

⁹ Sampson, *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research*, 9.

¹⁰ Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*, 59.

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Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.